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Sustainable synthesis of FDME from furfural and CO₂ using a mechanochemically prepared catalyst: Toward bio-based polyester monomerElizabeth Rangel-Rangel^{a,*}, Marta Iglesias^b, Eva M Maya^{b,*} ^a *Fundación Tecnológica Advantx (FUNDITEC), Faraday 7, CLAUD Building, Cantoblanco, Madrid 28049, Spain*^b *Instituto de Ciencia de Materiales de Madrid (ICMM-CSIC), Sor Juana Inés de la Cruz 3, Cantoblanco, Madrid 28049, Spain*

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ABSTRACT

A two-steps thermal process is reported for the sustainable synthesis of dimethyl furan-2,5-dicarboxylate (FDME), a valuable monomer in the production of bio-based polyesters. The route uses a bio-derived molecule, furfural (F), and CO₂ as raw materials. A mechanochemically synthesized hyper-crosslinked polymer (HCP) supported copper catalyst, was developed and applied in a sequential oxidation–carboxylation using moderate reaction pressures (P(O₂) and P(CO₂) of 6 and 10 bars, respectively), followed by acid-catalyzed esterification. The process was optimized using commercial CO₂, and further tested using simulated bio-based industrial CO₂ streams. Catalyst recyclability was demonstrated over five cycles with no loss in activity and the low E-factor (18.3 with methanol recycling and water removal), highlight the industrial and environmental potential for the FDME synthesis using this new route.

Furthermore, the FDME obtained was used directly, without purification, to synthesize a bio-based polyester by reaction with 1,3-propanediol. The resulting polymer showed comparable properties to those obtained from commercial FDME.

Introduction

Dimethyl furan-2,5-dicarboxylate (FDME) is a molecule highly sought after as a bio-based monomer which is displacing to furan-2,5-dicarboxylic acid (FDCA) due to its greater reactivity, solubility and the milder conditions required for its polymerization [1]. Thus, FDME, together with ethylene glycol, is used in the synthesis of polyethylene furanoate (PEF) a polyester known for its exceptional properties such as low melting temperature, high T_g (glass transition temperature) and outstanding gas barrier properties.

These characteristics make PEF a highly promising material for applications such as high-performance fibres and packaging [2]. Thus, PEF is emerging as strong candidate to replace polyethylene terephthalate (PET), the most widely used petroleum-derived thermoplastic polymer [2–4]. Besides, the reaction of FDME with other alcohols has the potential to create other innovative polyesters.

In recent years, several strategies have been developed to obtain FDME from bio-based molecules (Fig. 1, grey circle). The most common approach involves the oxidative esterification of 5-

hydroxymethylfurfural (HMF), a molecule derived from biomass through the dehydration of C6 sugars, using various homogeneous or heterogeneous metal-based catalysts [5–10]. Other approach includes the radical alkoxycarbonylation and alcoholysis of methyl furoate (MF), which achieves FDME in high yield (80 %) [11]. Using galactaric acid as the starting molecule, it is also possible to obtain FDME through esterification and dehydration reactions with yields between 50 and 70 % [12,13]. The last approach consists of the carboxylation-esterification reaction of 2-furic acid (FCA) under a CO₂ pressure of 8 bars. This method uses Cs₂CO₃ as a base in the first step, followed by methanol (MeOH) in the esterification step, which was also carried out under CO₂ pressure of 28 bar. Although this approach yields FDME with a moderate yield (66 %) due to equilibrium constraints and cesium intermediates remaining at the end of the reaction, it takes advantage of using CO₂ as a feedstock to introduce the carboxyl group into the final product [14]. Recently, in our research group, we have published the preparation of FDME by direct carboxylation of MF using a CO₂ pressure of 10 bars, a strong base such as Cs₂CO₃ and a cobalt-based heterogeneous catalyst. Despite being a very interesting strategy, FDME's performance was low,

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at 28 % [15]. Building on this work, and in an effort to improve the FDME yield, we decided to modify the catalyst and employ an alternative bio-based feedstock, such as furfural.

Furfural (F) is also an interesting bio-based molecule derived from the dehydration of C5 sugars and is recognized among the 30 significant core molecular precursors derived from biomass for the production of other value-added products [16,17], particularly C4 and C5 chemicals [18]. Recent works have highlighted the growing interest in similar topic, with two publications appearing during the writing of this manuscript. For instance, Tang and colleagues have reported the synthesis of furan-2,5-dicarboxylic acid (FDCA) from CO₂ and furfural through a homogeneous catalytic process [19], while Lee and collaborators have explored the production of FDCA ester via electrochemical carboxylation of Methyl-5-Bromo-2-Furoate (BrMF) [20].

Thus, the synthesis of FDME here reported consists in a two-step thermocatalytic process, using moderated gas pressures and a copper-based heterogeneous catalyst prepared by mechanochemical polymerization for the first step and acid-esterification with methanol for the second step (Fig. 1, green circle). Furthermore, to address potential industrial applications of this strategy, we have gone several steps further by exploring this process with CO₂ derived from simulated CO₂ bio-based industrial streams, estimating also the chemical efficiency of the process (E-factor). We have validated the FDME produced through this strategy by synthesizing a sustainable polyester that was also processed as a film. The novel polyester PPF has been compared with the same one prepared from commercial FDME derived from petroleum. This is also an important contribution of this work since few works have been reported of bio-based polyesters prepared from CO₂-based monomers [21,22].

Experimental

Materials and methods

o-Phenylenediamine (99 %) was supplied by FEROSA and Salicylaldehyde (99 %) by Thermo Scientific; Iron (III) chloride (98 %) was provided by Fisher Chemical; Carbon dioxide (99.9 % of purity) was obtained by Praxair. Synthetic Carbon dioxide mixtures (97.5–99.97 % of purity) simulating CO₂ streams from bio-based industries were supplied by Lindle.

Furfural (99.0 %) and Cs₂CO₃ (99.5 %), were obtained from Across Organics; Dimethoxymethane (98 %) was purchased by Alfa Aesar; copper (II) acetate monohydrate (98 %) was supplied by Strem Chemicals; Dimethyl furan-2, 5-dicarboxylate (99 %) (for comparative purposes) was supplied by Apollo Scientific. Titanium tetraisopropoxide was purchased from Merck (97 %) and 1,3-propanediol (99.6 %) was obtained by Sigma-Aldrich.

All reagents were utilized without further purification. All solvents were obtained from JT Baker.

Synthesis of *N,N'*-phenylenebis(salicylideneimine) (salphen)

This monomer was synthesized following the procedure reported [23]. Thus, salicylaldehyde (4 g, 32.8 mmol) and *o*-phenylenediamine (1.7 g, 16.4 mmol) were dissolved in 50 mL of methanol. The mixture was refluxed at 70 °C for 3 h. After partial solvent evaporation, crystallization was induced by adding petroleum ether. Afterward, the crystals obtained were filtered on a Buchner yielding an orange solid (5 g, 16 mmol, 95 %). ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 13.09 (d, 2H), 8.65 (s, 2H), 7.46 – 7.33 (m, 6H), 7.25 (m, 2H), 7.07 (m, 2H), 6.94 (m, 2H). Elemental analysis, (C₂₀H₁₆N₂O₂) Calculated: C, 75.93; H, 5.10; N, 8.86 Found: C, 77.25; H, 5.19; N, 7.84.

Fig. 1. Reported FDME synthesis (grey circle) and contributions of this work (green circle). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Synthesis of copper-based catalyst (HCP-Salphen-Cu) by mechanochemical polymerization

A zirconia vessel containing three zirconia balls was charged with 500 mg (1.58 mmol) of the salphen monomer and 1.3 g (8 mmol) of iron (III) chloride. To this, 0.7 mL (8.0 mmol) of dimethoxymethane was added. The mixture was subjected to ball milling at 600 rpm for 55 min. Upon completion, methanol was introduced to the vessel, and the resulting solid product was separated by filtration. The solid was sequentially washed with ammonium hydroxide, diluted hydrochloric acid, and water, followed by purification via Soxhlet extraction using methanol for 24 h. Finally, the material was dried under vacuum at 100 °C for 24 h. 465 mg (93 % yield) of HCP-Salphen support were attained as a brown powder.

HCP-Salphen was mixed with $\text{Cu}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (160 mg, 0.9 mmol) dissolved in 20 mL of EtOH and heated at 80 °C for 24 h. After cooled down to room temperature the product was isolated through filtration and subsequently rinsed with methanol. It was dried in a vacuum oven at 100 °C for 12 h, yielding 525 mg of HCP-Salphen-Cu as a dark brown powder.

Synthesis of FDME from furfural and CO_2

Furfural (1.5 mmol, 144 mg), HCP-Salphen-Cu (180 mg, 1.8 % Cu), Cs_2CO_3 (730 mg, 2.25 mmol) and some drops of water were introduced in a high-pressure reactor (Autoclave Engineers®). The reactor was purged 3 times and then pressurized with O_2 (6 bar) and heated at 60 °C for 5 h. After this time, the O_2 was released, and the reactor was purged 3 times with CO_2 and filled with CO_2 at 10 bar. This mixture was heated at 200 °C for 7 h. After cooling, anhydrous MeOH (10 mL) was added and the catalyst, HCP-Salphen-Cu was removed by filtration. Subsequently, some drops of H_2SO_4 were added to the reaction mixture at room temperature to induce precipitation of cesium sulfate (731 mg, 2.02 mmol) which was removed by filtration. Finally, H_2SO_4 (drops until pH = 1–2) was added and the mixture was heated at 80 °C for 24 h. The solvent is almost completely removed in a rotary evaporator and 2 mL of cool water are added to obtain FDME which was isolated as a beige solid. The crude FDME was dissolved in dichloromethane, and activated carbon was added and stirred for 10 min. After filtration to remove the activated carbon and subsequent evaporation of the solvent, FDME was obtained as a white solid.

The reaction was followed by thin-layer chromatography (TLC) and ^1H NMR.

Recycling experiments

Furfural (3 mmol, 288 mg), HCP-Salphen-Cu catalyst (360 mg, 1.8 % Cu), and Cs_2CO_3 (1.46 g, 5.50 mmol), along with a few drops of water, were introduced into a high-pressure reactor (Autoclave Engineers®). The reactor was purged three times with oxygen and then pressurized with O_2 to 6 bar. The mixture was heated at 60 °C for 5 h. After the oxidation step, the reactor was depressurized to release the O_2 , purged three times with CO_2 , and then re-pressurized to 10 bar with CO_2 . The system was subsequently heated to 200 °C and maintained at this temperature for 7 h. Upon cooling to room temperature, anhydrous methanol (20 mL) was added. The catalyst (HCP-Salphen-Cu) was recovered by filtration, thoroughly washed with methanol and acetone to remove any adsorbed organic residues, and dried overnight at 100 °C prior to reuse. This catalytic process was repeated up to five cycles using fresh furfural and Cs_2CO_3 in each cycle, while reusing the recovered catalyst.

Synthesis of poly(propylene 2,5-furandicarboxylate) (PPF)

A mixture of FDME (200 mg, 1.08 mmol), 1,3-propanediol (250 mg, 3.25 mmol) and $\text{Ti}(\text{OiPr})_4$ (2 % mmol related to the FDME amount) was dissolved in a small amount of dry toluene (1 mL) in a 25 mL round-bottom flask containing a magnetic stir bar. The flask was fitted with a distillation adapter linked to a vacuum pump, allowing the system to be evacuated to remove air before being purged and filled with nitrogen gas. After five evacuating and filling cycles, the flask was heated to 160 °C for 1 h using an aluminium-heating block, at 170 °C for an additional 1 h and finally at 180 °C for 0.5 h to carry out the transesterification reaction. After 2.5 h of reaction, the vacuum was gradually introduced to eliminate the excess of alcohol. Subsequently, the temperature was increased to 200 °C. After 90 min, the polycondensation was stopped, cooled and the polyester was removed by adding chloroform and trifluoroacetic acid (2:1 v/v). The polyester was precipitated by adding methanol. Following vacuum filtration and rinsing with methanol, the product was dried under vacuum at 100 °C, resulting in 220 mg of a white-beige solid with a quantitative yield.

For comparative purposes, poly(propylene 2,5-furandicarboxylate) (c-PPF) was also prepared using the above synthetic procedure and commercial FDME.

Poly(propylene 2,5-furandicarboxylate) film preparation

Films from PPF were prepared by solvent casting and by compression molding.

Solvent casting: 100 mg of PPF were dissolved in a 0.5 mL of a mixture of chloroform and trifluoroacetic acid (1:1). The solution was transferred onto a leveled glass plate confined by a ring to ensure uniform thickness, and covered with a funnel to allow the solvent to evaporate slowly at room temperature. Finally, the film was detached from the surface and dried overnight at 50 °C.

Compression molding: This film was prepared using a Specac press with Upilex foils as separators on both sides. First, 100 mg of PPF were melted at 110 °C for 1 min. Then, a pressure of 150 bar was applied for 3 min. Finally, the film was rapidly cooled by removing it from the press at 110 °C.

Equipment and characterization techniques

Mechanical milling was carried out using a Retsch PM100 planetary ball mill equipped with 50 mL steel-jacketed zirconia grinding vessels (Fritsch), 2 cm zirconia milling media, and Viton O-ring seals.

The catalytic tests were taken on an Autoclave Engineers® reactor. FTIR-ATR spectra were performed in a spectral range of 400–4000 cm^{-1} in a Bruker Vertex 70v with a resolution of 2 cm^{-1} .

Proton nuclear magnetic resonance (^1H NMR) spectra were done in a BRUKER AVANCE III HD (Larmor frequencies of 400) using CDCl_3 or D_2O as solvents. This technique was used to determine the structures of all the compounds presented in this article, and to carry out the optimization of the catalytic activity.

Melting points were measured in a Stuart Scientific SMP-1 apparatus.

The HRMS analyses were done in an Agilent 1200 Series LC system (equipped with a binary pump, an autosampler, and a column oven) coupled to a 6520 quadrupole-time of flight (QTOF) mass spectrometer. Acetonitrile: water (75:25, v:v) was used as mobile phase at 0.2 mL min^{-1} . The ionization source was an ESI interface working in the positive-ion mode.

X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS) measurements were carried out using a SPECS GmbH instrument equipped with a PHOIBOS 150 9MCD hemispherical energy analyzer. A non-monochromatic magnesium X-ray source operating at 200 W power and 12 kV voltage was employed. Samples were initially placed in the pre-chamber at room temperature and degassed for several hours prior to transfer into the analysis chamber. Survey spectra and high-resolution scans were

recorded using pass energies of 50 eV and 20 eV, respectively.

The thermal stability of the catalysts and polyesters was studied by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) using a TQ-500 apparatus from TA Instruments. The experiments were carried out under an air atmosphere at the heating rate of $10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$ to a final temperature of $850\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ using between 3–5 mg of sample.

The glass transition temperatures (T_g) of the polyesters were measured using differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) on a TA Instruments Q-100 device. Samples were sealed in standard aluminum pans and initially heated from ambient temperature to $350\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ at a rate of $10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C per minute}$ to erase any prior thermal history. Following this, the specimens were cooled and reheated, with the T_g values determined from the inflection points observed in the heat flow versus temperature curves during the second heating cycle.

Nitrogen adsorption–desorption measurements were conducted using a Micromeritics ASAP 2020 M porosity analyzer at 77 K. Prior to analysis, samples were degassed overnight at $120\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to remove impurities. Specific surface areas were calculated applying the BET method, while average pore sizes were estimated using the BJH technique.

CO_2 adsorption isotherms were collected with a Micromeritics ASAP 2010 volumetric system. Approximately 60 mg of powdered sample was loaded into a sample holder, which was submerged in a Julabo FP40-HL recirculating thermostatic bath to maintain a constant adsorption temperature of 273 K.

Before adsorption experiments, the samples were outgassed at 423 K for 6 h using a turbo-molecular high vacuum pump.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) micrographs were recorded in a Hitachi SU-8000 microscope operating at 0.5 kV. The samples were directly dispersed onto a double-sided adhesive surface.

Average molecular weight (Mw) was obtained using an Agilent GPC 1260 Infinity II equipment provided with a 1260 Infinity II Viscometer as a detector and with a PLgel 5 μm MIXED- 300 x 7.5 mm Column. Standards kit of Poly(styrene) was used (medium low; Mp 162-851000 Da; 12x 1 g (PSS Polymer Standards Service GmbH, Germany) for column calibration and system calibration.

The PPF film prepared by compression molding was obtained using a Specac press with Upilex foils as separators on both sides.

Results and discussion

Synthesis and characterization of the catalyst (HCP-Salphen-Cu)

According to the literature, to carry out oxidation or carboxylation reactions on furfural derivatives, transition metal copper-complexes could be good options [8,11,24] while esterification reaction can be made by using acid-catalysis [25]. A hyper-crosslinked polymer (HCP) was selected as an ideal support for the catalytic active centers because of its proven efficiency in preparing versatile heterogeneous catalysts for various organic transformations [26,27]. In addition to metals, HCPs have incorporated other active sites, such as basic [28,29], acid [29,30] and ionic liquids [31–33], to catalyze diverse reactions. While conventional HCP synthesis typically requires toxic chlorinated solvents and long reaction times (24–72 h), mechanochemical polymerization of this type of networks, introduced in 2019 [34], offers a more sustainable alternative, avoiding solvents and reducing reaction times to 5–60 min. Furthermore, it is a strategy that has recently been successfully used in our research group to synthesize a cobalt catalyst from the same salphen ligand [15]. Thus, in this work, the catalyst HCP-Salphen-Cu was prepared following the same strategy, that is by immobilizing copper on an HCP support synthesized by mechanochemical polymerization (Fig. 2).

N,N'-phenylenebis(salicylideneimine) (Salphen) was selected as ligand because has a N_2O_2 -type tetradentate structure that are capable of establishing robust NNOO -metal bonds, providing a highly stable coordination framework relative to other ligands. Besides, it has previously been incorporated into HCPs to coordinate other metals such as palladium or aluminium [27]. Thus, the starting support, HCP-Salphen was prepared by mechanochemical polymerization in 55 min using Salphen as the monomer, FeCl_3 as the catalyst and dimetoxymethane as the crosslinker. The first evidence of the growth of the hyper-crosslinked network was the formation of a dark brown solid insoluble in common solvents. HCP-Salphen support was mixed with $\text{Cu}(\text{OAc})_2$ in ethanol to incorporate the corresponding copper cations on the polymeric backbone.

As shown in Fig. 3a, the FT-IR spectrum displays a distinct peak at 1610 cm^{-1} along with a nearby signal at 1579 cm^{-1} , both associated with the $\text{C}=\text{N}-\text{Cu}$ coordination. Additional bands appear at 1538 and 1435 cm^{-1} , corresponding to $\text{C}=\text{C}$ vibrations. Peaks observed at 1210 and 1161 cm^{-1} are assigned to $\text{C}-\text{N}$ and $\text{C}-\text{O}$ bond vibrations, respectively. The spectral profile closely resembles that of previously studied HCP-Salphen-metal complexes [35], and also shares features with the

Fig. 2. Synthesis of the HCP-Salphen-catalyst using a mechanochemical approach.

Fig. 3. a) FT-IR spectra, c) TGA and d) N_2 adsorption-desorption isotherms of HCP-Salphen and HCP-Salphen-Cu; b) XPS Cu_{2p} traces, e) CO_2 adsorption isotherm and f) SEM image of HCP-Salphen-Cu.

unmetalated HCP-Salphen support, which displays a peak near 1600 cm^{-1} due to imine (C=N) stretching, along with another signal at 1577 cm^{-1} that may suggest partial coordination of iron to the imine groups.

The copper content was determined by inductively coupled plasma (ICP) spectroscopy and was found to be 10 % (1.6 mmol/g) of Cu. This proportion of copper indicates that, two out of three salphen units are coordinated to copper centers. The presence of the metal was also confirmed by XPS (Fig. 3b). Two peaks at 936.11 eV attributed to Cu 2p_{3/2} and at 956.07 eV due to Cu 2p_{1/2} and the corresponding satellite lines, typical for Cu(II) compounds [36] confirmed the effective incorporation of copper into the HCP. The C1s spectrum shows (Fig. S1) two peaks at 286.40 and 287.68 eV corresponding to C–C and C–N bonds and the N1s spectrum (Fig. S1) exhibits a single peak centred at 401.26 eV assigned to the effective formation of imine bonds (N=C). Finally, the analysis shows a signal at 534.30 eV attributed to the O 1 s bonds (Fig. S1).

The thermograms indicated that the incorporation of copper decreases the thermal stability (Fig. 3c) since the HCP-Salphen showed a first of decomposition with a starting temperature of 270 °C while for HCP-Salphen-Cu the decomposition starts at 215 °C. The HCP-Salphen thermogram showed a residue of 10.04 %. Considering that during the thermal analysis in an oxidizing atmosphere, Fe₂O₃ is formed, it was possible to calculate the amount of iron present in this polymer, which was 6.98 %. In the case of HCP-Salphen-Cu, the residue was quite higher, 23.7 %, which indicates that besides the Fe₂O₃, CuO (13.66 %) was formed during the analysis which correspond to a copper content of 10.7 %, similar to the amount obtained by ICP. Table S1 shows the elemental analysis of both HCPs.

The porous properties of HCP-Salphen-Cu and its precursor were evaluated by N₂ adsorption–desorption isotherms (Fig. 3d). The nitrogen adsorption isotherm of HCP-Salphen exhibited uptake at low relative pressures, suggesting the presence of microporosity. As the pressure increased, a moderate adsorption was observed, corresponding to a calculated specific surface area of 94.7 $\text{m}^2\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$. Upon incorporation of copper, the surface area significantly decreased to 12.08 $\text{m}^2\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$, likely due to partial pore blockage by the metal species—a behavior commonly reported in metal-functionalized hyper-crosslinked polymers [37].

The CO₂ uptake was measured for HCP-Salphen-Cu by CO₂ adsorption isotherm (Fig. 3e) indicating a low CO₂ uptake (0.70 mmol/g) compared to most of the previously reported HCPs [38–40]. This fact can be attributed to the absence of specific CO₂-philic groups in the HCPs of this work.

The surface morphology was studied by SEM (scanning electron microscopy) (Fig. 3f) revealing the typical morphology of a porous crosslinked polymer with spherical structures and agglomerates despite the moderate porosity parameters.

CO₂-based synthesis of dimethyl furan-2,5-dicarboxylate (FDME)

Reaction optimization

The synthesis of FDME from furfural and CO₂ presents a significant challenge due to both the kinetic and thermodynamic limitations

associated with CO₂ [41], as well as the low reactivity of the carbon atom at the 5-position of furfural [14]. The strategy reported here consists of a two-step process without the need to isolate the reaction intermediate, cesium furan-2,5-dicarboxylate (FDCACs) (Fig. 4).

In the first step, two consecutive reactions were done, an oxidation and subsequent carboxylation of furfural using the copper-based catalyst and the second step involves an acid-esterification reaction which can be done by conventional strategies using methanol and a few drops of sulfuric acid.

The oxidation-carboxylation step had to be optimized (Table 1). The first tests were carried out with copper acetate as the catalyst and cesium carbonate as the base. Different reaction conditions were used and it was found that FDCACs was selectively obtained in moderate-low yield (25 %) using a furfural/copper/Cs₂CO₃ ratio of 1/0.02/1.5, 6 bar (PO₂), 90 °C and 5 h of reaction, and then, after the O₂ was released, the reactor was filled with CO₂ (10 bar) and heated at 200 °C for 5 h (entry 1). By decreasing the temperature to 60 °C an improvement of the yield was achieved (37 %, entry 2). This result encouraged us to use the heterogeneous catalyst HCP-Salphen-Cu in the same above conditions obtaining FDCACs in lower yield than the copper salt precursor (30 %) (entry 3). However, an increase in the reaction time of two hours resulted in an FDCACs yield of 47 %, which could not be improved even with increases in time or temperature.

The reaction was also done by doubling the amount of furfural and all the other reagents, obtaining the same FDCACs yield (entry 6). Although the yield of FDCACs was initially moderate, by employing furfural and a copper-based catalyst, we achieved a more than 60 % increase in yield compared to previous work that used methyl furoate and a cobalt catalyst as starting materials, representing a significant improvement in reaction efficiency [15]. Besides, in this stage, degradation products that are not detectable by conventional methods are likely formed, a phenomenon also noted by Banerjee et al. during the CO₂ insertion to 2-furanoic acid [14].

Thus, after optimizing the first step, the HCP-Salphen-Cu was removed by filtration and after the addition of MeOH, the esterification of FDCACs was done using some drops of sulfuric acid and heating the mixture at 80 °C for 24 h to obtain FDME in quantitative yield (entries 4 and 6). The reaction was also carried out without isolation of the FDCACs, obtaining the same result.

Three control experiments were also done to verify the role of the catalyst, O₂ and CO₂ in the reaction (entries 7–11). As can be observed, in the absence of a catalyst or using the metal-free support (HCP-Salphen) no reaction took place. By using FeCl₃ as a catalyst, to assess a possible contribution in case this species of iron would remain as a residue in the catalyst but no FDCACs was obtained in this run (entry 9). Thus, these experiments confirm the essential role of the copper complex in this sequential reaction. Finally, the control experiment conducted in the absence of CO₂ (entry 11) confirmed its essential role in the reaction, strongly supporting the conclusion that CO₂ is required as a reagent in the carboxylation step.

Fig. 4. CO₂-based synthesis of FDME from Furfural.

Table 1
Optimization of the reaction^{a)}.

Entry	Catalyst	Cs ₂ CO ₃ (mmol)	O ₂ P (bar)	T (°C)	t (h)	CO ₂ P (bar)	T (°C)	t (h)	FDCACs Yield ^{c)} (Sel. %) ^{d)}	FDME ^{b)} Yield ^{c)} (Sel.%) ^{d)}
1	Cu(CH ₃ COO) ₂	1.5	6	90	5	10	200	5	25 (100)	
2		1.5	6	60	5	10	200	5	37 (100)	
3	HCP-Salphen-Cu	1.5	6	60	5	10	200	5	30 (100)	
4		1.5	6	60	5	10	200	7	47 (100)	100 (100)
5		1.5	6	60	5	10	210	9	22 (100)	
6		3	6	60	5	10	200	7	47 (100)	100 (100)
7	none	1.5	6	60	5	10	200	7	–	
8	HCP-Salphen	1.5	6	60	5	10	200	7	–	
9	FeCl ₃	1.5	6	60	5	10	200	7	–	
10	HCP-Salphen-Cu	1.5	–	60	5	10	200	7	–	
11	HCP-Salphen-Cu	1.5	6	60	5	–	200	7	–	

a) For all reactions expect entry 6: oxidation-carboxylation step to obtain FDCACs: Furfural (F) = 1 mmol, Catalysts (0.02 mmol (1.8 w% based on metal content); solvent-free; b) esterification step: to obtain FDME from FDCACs: MeOH anh. = 10 mL, drops of up to acid pH, 80 °C, 24 h; c) Isolated yields, calculated by weighing the products and comparing it to the theoretical amount based on the starting material; d) Determined by ¹H NMR spectroscopy (100 % selectivity was assigned since no signals corresponding to side products or unreacted starting materials were observed).

Isolation and characterization of the intermediate product (FDCACs) and dimethyl furan-2,5-dicarboxylate (FDME)

The cesium furan-2,5-dicarboxylate (FDCACs) obtained after the oxidation-carboxylation step was separated from the catalyst and analyzed by ¹H NMR (Fig. 5b). As can be observed, the spectrum showed a unique signal at 7.3 ppm, which was attributed to the protons of the furan ring as it was previously reported for this compound [14], and the

complete absence of any signs attributed to the starting furfural (Fig. 5a). The ¹H NMR of FDME exhibits two signals at 7.3 and 3.8 ppm that correspond to the protons of the furan ring and the methyl groups respectively which confirming the formation of methyl esters. This spectrum was compared with that of the commercial FMDE (Fig. S2) which exhibited the same signals.

In addition, FDME synthesized with the new process was compared

Fig. 5. ¹H NMR spectra of a) Furfural (F); b) FDCACs and c) FMDE.

with the commercial one by other characterization techniques. FT-IR spectra (Fig. S3) of both diesters showed a strong absorption at 1714 cm^{-1} attributed to the stretching vibration of the carbonyl groups; the absorptions at 584, 1435, 1270, 1190–900 and 736 cm^{-1} attributed to the stretching vibrations of the furan ring skeleton and absorption peaks between 3330 and 3290 cm^{-1} assigned to the C–H stretching vibration of the furan rings. The thermogravimetric analysis of both monomers was also compared (Fig. S4) observing the same decomposition pattern in one step but with slightly different starting degradation temperatures being the commercial monomer more stable. Finally, Fig. S5 shows the HRMS spectrum which also confirms the chemical structure of this monomer.

The melting point of FDME of this work was 99–101 °C which agrees well with that reported for FDME prepared by radical alkoxy-carbonylation and alcoholysis of methyl furoate (MF) (101–102 °C) [11].

Although a comprehensive mechanistic study is outside the primary scope of this work, which is focused on the development and validation of a sustainable process, a plausible mechanism can be proposed based on our experimental observations and supported by previously reported mechanisms for the oxidation [42–44] and carboxylation of furan derivatives [14,24,41]. This proposal (Fig. S6) offers a rational explanation of the observed reactivity and product distribution.

Recyclability of the catalyst

The recyclability of a catalyst is an important factor supporting its viability in industrial applications. Thus, the recyclability of the catalyst of this process was evaluated carrying out the reaction up to 5 consecutive times (Fig. 6). HCP-Salphen-Cu was separated after the oxidation-carboxylation and it was washed with MeOH for 30 min and dried at 100 °C overnight under vacuum to be used in new runs. The FDCACs yield was maintained in all runs which confirmed the recyclability of the catalyst.

The FT-IR spectrum (Fig. S7a) indicated that the structure of the catalyst was maintained after five consecutive reactions along with thermal stability (Fig. S7b). The conventional leaching experiment could not be carried out because it was solvent-free reaction. Thus, the ICP-OES analysis of the recovered HCP-Salphen-Cu was carried out showing a Cu content of 9.3 % and the XPS spectra (Fig. S8) also confirmed that the chemical composition and electronic state of the elements were maintained after the reactions.

Fig. 6. Recycling experiments of HCP-Salphen-Cu in the oxidation-carboxylation reaction.

Initial assessment of the industrial feasibility of the process

To get closer to potential industrial applications, the process was conducted using three different CO_2 sources, each derived from simulated bio-based industrial streams (Fig. 7). The yields of the FDCACs using mixtures 2 and 3 were lower than those using the commercial CO_2 probably due to the presence of traces of CO and H_2S , which poison the copper-based catalyst [45,46]. Thus, catalyst protection or reactivation processes should be carried out in order to use streams with these compositions. However, when using Mixture 1, the catalyst exhibited a performance comparable to that observed with high-purity commercial CO_2 despite the presence of traces of nitrogen dioxide [47]. This indicates that the process is potentially compatible with certain industrial CO_2 sources and demonstrate a notable tolerance to common impurities.

The chemical efficiency of the process was also estimated by the environmental factor (E-factor = mass of waste/mass of product,) [48]. Considering three waste products, cesium sulfate, methanol and water, an E-factor of 111.8 was obtained (information on calculation in the SI). However, methanol could be recycled and reused in the same process once the water was removed. In their synthesis of FMDE from 5-hydroxymethylfurfural (HMF), Sun et al. reported a 14 % loss of organic solvent during recovery, a factor that can be accounted for when adjusting the E-factor [49]. Therefore, when water is removed and methanol is recycled, the E-factor is calculated to be 18.3, placing it within the acceptable waste range for the chemical industry (5–50) [48] and falling within the range reported for FDME synthesis via oxidative esterification of HMF (2.5–55.4). Thus, the E factor was considerably reduced to 18.3 by incorporating water removal and methanol recycling into the process. This adjustment led to a marked decrease in waste production and highlights the progress in FDME synthesis from Furfural and CO_2 toward greater sustainability and compliance with green chemistry principles.

Synthesis of poly(propylene2,5-furandicarboxylate) (PPF)

As a proof of validation, the FDME obtained by the novel process, was reacted with 1,3-propanediol without any further purification to obtain poly(propylene 2,5-furandicarboxylate) (PPF, Fig. 8). The reaction was carried out by adapting the procedure reported for the synthesis of high-performance polyesters from other furane-based monomers [50–52].

Thus, FDME prepared from furfural and CO_2 , 1,3-propanediol and titanium isopropoxide were heated at 160 °C under an N_2 atmosphere for 1 h, at 170 °C for 1 h more and at 180 °C for 0.5 h to complete the transesterification reaction. Next, vacuum was slowly introduced to eliminate the surplus diol. The temperature was then raised to 200 °C and held steady for 90 min to facilitate melt polycondensation. Afterward, the reaction mixture was allowed to cool to 30 °C, and the polyester was extracted by dissolving it in a chloroform and trifluoroacetic acid solution (2:1). Finally, the addition of methanol caused the polyester to precipitate as a beige solid.

For comparative purposes, a polyester derived from commercial FDME was also synthesized using the same procedure and referred as c-PPF. This polyester and other PPF reported in the literature have been used for comparative purposes [53–56].

Both polyesters were characterized by FT-IR, ^1H NMR, TGA, DSC and X-Ray (Fig. 9 and S7). The FT-IR (Fig. 9a) of both polyesters were similar showing the strong absorption due to the stretching vibration of the carbonyl groups at 1713 cm^{-1} . The absorptions attributed to the stretching vibrations of the furan ring skeleton appear at the same wavenumbers at 1570, 1266, 1220, 1034–825 and 750 cm^{-1} but are slightly shifted with respect to the precursor monomers. The absorption assigned to the C–H stretching vibration of the furan rings appears between 3330 and 3290 cm^{-1} in both polyesters but the CH_2 stretching vibrations coming from the propanediol showed slightly different wavenumbers, at 1426 cm^{-1} in the c-PPF and at 1460 cm^{-1} in the PPF. Both ^1H NMR spectra (Fig. 9b) showed two signals at 2.37 and 4.65 ppm attributed to the methylene groups and another signal at 7.40 ppm due

Components	Mixture 1	Mixture 2	Mixture 3
CO ₂ (vol%)	99.97	99.62	97.5
O ₂ (vol%)	0.034	-	2.4
N ₂ (vol%)	-	0.38	-
H ₂ O (ppm)	-	-	-
CH ₄ (ppm)	-	-	1000
H ₂ S (ppm)	-	-	7
CO (ppm)	-	0.5	-
NO (ppm)	-	4	-
NO ₂ (ppm)	5	-	-
FDCACs Yield	47 %	15 %	10%
FDME Yield	100 %	100 %	100%

Fig. 7. Composition of simulated CO₂ streams derived from bio-based industries and yields achieved in the synthesis of FDCACs and FDME.

Fig. 8. Synthesis of poly(propylene 2,5-furandicarboxylate) (PPF) from FDME of this work.

to the protons of the furan ring which were coincident with the reported [51,52]. However, the ¹H NMR spectrum of PPF indicated more purity for this polyester than for c-PPF. The TGAs (Fig. 9c) were similar since both polyesters exhibited a decomposition in two stages with a starting degradation temperature of 350 °C. The TGAs were quite similar to that of the reported PPFs [51,52,54].

The DSC (Fig. 9d) showed some differences between the two polyesters. The T_g of the novel PPF was 40 °C, whereas a lower T_g (23 °C) was observed for the c-PPF. Both values are lower than those reported for other PPFs, which range between 47 °C [52] and 58 °C [51]. The DSC of PPF did not show any other thermal transition like the PPFs reported [51,53,54]. However, the DSC of c-PPF showed crystallinity and melting peaks at 97 °C and 146 °C, respectively which indicates a certain crystalline character for this polyester. The X-Ray diffractograms (Fig. S9) confirm the amorphous nature of the novel PPF and the moderated semi-crystallinity of c-PPF with the presence of two peaks at 2θ = 16 and at 2θ = 30.

The novel polyester showed was also analyzed by GPC (Fig. S10) showing an average molecular weight of 26650 g/mol and could be processed into films by casting and compression molding (Fig. S11). Since polyester is naturally obtained with a beige color, we attribute the dark coloration of the films to the processing conditions.

Conclusions

A thermo-catalyzed two-step process has been developed to obtain a monomer of high industrial value, dimethyl Furan-2,5-dicarboxylate (FDME) starting for the first time, furfural and CO₂ as renewable feedstocks. This transformation represents a significant challenge due to both the intrinsic kinetic and thermodynamic limitations of CO₂ and the low reactivity at the C5 position of furfural.

The process employs a tailor-made heterogeneous catalyst based on copper coordinated to a Salphen ligand, supported on a hyper-

crosslinked polymer (HCP) synthesized via mechanochemical polymerization, a solvent-free and time-efficient alternative to conventional methods. This approach reduces polymerization time dramatically from 24 to 72 h to just 55 min.

In the first step, a sequential oxidation-carboxylation reaction is carried out using HCP-Salphen-Cu as a catalyst, and cesium carbonate as a base, in a solvent-free reaction: 60 °C under O₂ (6 bar) for 5 h followed by at 200 °C under CO₂ (10 bar) for 7 h. This yields cesium furan-2,5-dicarboxylate (FDCACs) as a reaction intermediate in a 47 % yield without requiring isolation. In the second step, after catalyst removal by filtration, acidified methanol is added and the mixture is heated at 80 °C for 24 h to yield FDME quantitatively. This strategy achieves a >60 % increase in yield compared to previous methods using methyl furoate and cobalt catalysts.

The catalyst demonstrated excellent recyclability, maintaining full activity over five consecutive runs. Furthermore, the process was compatible with simulated CO₂ streams mimicking industrial bio-based sources. When water removal and methanol recycling is considered, the process achieves a favorable E-factor of 18.3, underscoring its alignment with green chemistry principles.

The resulting high-purity FDME was successfully polymerized with 1,3-propanediol to form poly(propylene 2,5-furandicarboxylate) (PPF). The polymer exhibited properties suitable for film formation, confirming the potential of FDME as a key monomer for bio- and CO₂-based polyesters. These interesting results are a gateway to obtaining new bio- and CO₂-based polyesters from this key monomer.

Overall, this work provides a promising route for sustainable FDME production from renewable feedstocks and opens new opportunities for the development of CO₂-derived bioplastics with industrial relevance.

This work provides proof of concept for a scalable and greener process that integrates CO₂ valorization and biomass-derived feedstocks.

Fig. 9. a) FT-IR spectra; b) ^1H NMR spectra; c) TGA and d) DSC of PPF and c-PPF.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Elizabeth Rangel-Rangel: Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Marta Iglesias:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Data curation. **Eva M Maya:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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